

The Effect of Brand Awareness on Brand Image and Purchase Decisions: A Study of Club Bottled Water in Mataram City

Yuliana Sentia¹, Handayani Rinuastuti²

¹Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Mataram, Mataram, Indonesia

²Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Mataram, Mataram, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the effect of Brand Awareness on Brand Image and Purchase Decisions of Club brand bottled drinking water in Mataram City. The type of research used is quantitative research with associative causality method. The population in this study are consumers of Club brand bottled drinking water who live in Mataram City. The research sample was 100 respondents selected using purposive sampling technique with the criteria of having purchased Club brand bottled drinking water products. Data analysis was carried out using SmartPLS software version 4.1.1.5. The results showed that Brand Awareness was proven to have a positive and significant effect on Purchasing Decisions both directly and through Brand Image.

KEYWORD: Brand Awareness, Purchase Decision, Brand Image

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, public awareness of the importance of consuming clean and healthy water has increased. This has made bottled drinking water (AMDK) one of the most promising market commodities. (Pratiwi et al., 2025) stated that the trend in bottled drinking water consumption is driven by the public's need for clean and safe water, as well as a more practical lifestyle. Furthermore, this trend has encouraged various bottled drinking water brands to emerge on the market, creating intense competition among brands in the industry.

One of the most well-known bottled water products is *Club*, a brand of bottled water from Indonesia (Widiaswara, 2017). Club is widely known in the national market, as part of the competitive and growing bottled water industry. The existence of the Club brand reflects the dynamics of the mineral water market in Indonesia, which continues to grow along with changes in consumer consumption patterns. According to data from the Top Brand Award 2021-2024, Club brand bottled water experienced a significant decline in sales every year. Club brand bottled water products always ranked lowest compared to other drinking water products. In 2024, it was the lowest year for Club brand bottled water sales because sales of this product only reached 3.30%. Intense competition in the bottled water industry requires every company to be able to design the right marketing strategy to build a competitive advantage while maintaining consumer loyalty (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

From a marketing perspective, a good product is one that is able to create strong brand awareness in the minds of consumers. As stated by Rosmayanti (2023), brand awareness is an important aspect in the purchasing decision process because it is the starting point of consumer interaction with a brand. Without brand awareness, a product will not enter the consumer's consideration set, which is a collection of brands that are truly considered before making a purchase (Keller, 2013). Emma's (2000) research shows that consumers are more likely to choose brands they already know even though there are other alternatives, because awareness functions as a heuristic or shortcut in decision making. In addition, brand awareness can reduce the risk perceived by consumers because they are more confident and feel safe buying familiar brands (Moisescu, 2009). Brand awareness is the ability of consumers to recognize or remember a brand as part of a particular product category (Aaker, 1991b). Brand awareness is not only limited to recognizing a logo or brand name, but also includes remembering slogans, packaging colors, and experiences of interacting with the product (Krisnawati, 2016).

Several previous studies, such as those conducted by (Zhang et al., 2020); Melinia et al., (2024); Rachmah and Andari, (2022); have proven that brand awareness has a significant influence on purchasing decisions. However, different findings were shown by (Rania et al., 2023) and (Putri et al., 2024) where brand awareness was proven to have no significant influence on purchasing decisions. In addition to playing a role in shaping consumer behavior such as purchasing decisions, brand awareness

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plays an important role in shaping brand image because consumer awareness of a brand is the gateway to forming deeper perceptions (Rachmawati & Akbar, 2025) . High brand awareness enables the formation of a positive brand image, because consumers have sufficient information and experience to assess the quality of a product (Kotler & Keller, 2016) . (Aaker, 1991b) also emphasized that the higher the level of brand awareness, the greater the opportunity for a brand to build positive associations that then form a strong brand image. A positive brand image will influence purchasing decisions, because consumers tend to choose brands that have a good image and align with their expectations. This provides an initial overview of the possibility of Brand Image playing a role as a predictor of purchasing decisions, or as an intermediary in the direct relationship between Brand Awareness and Purchasing Decisions. A positive brand image will increase consumer trust, strengthen perceptions of quality, and ultimately drive purchasing decisions (Hanifah & Wulandari, 2021) .

Several previous studies, such as those conducted by Henny et al., (2022), stated that brand awareness has a positive and significant influence on brand image . (Wiranata & Bernarto, 2020) also shows that Brand Awareness has a significant influence on the emergence of Brand Image in the minds of consumers, as well as demonstrating the role of Brand Image as an intermediary in the direct relationship of Brand Awareness to consumer behavior such as purchasing decisions.

Based on the above phenomena and the inconsistencies in previous research, this study aims to analyze in more depth the influence of *brand awareness* on *brand image* and consumer purchasing decisions for Club brand bottled drinking water products in Mataram City. Therefore, this study is entitled " **The Effect of Brand Awareness on Brand Image and Purchase Decisions: A Study of Club Bottled Water in Mataram City.**"

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Purchase Decisions

Purchasing decisions are a decision-making process for purchases that includes determining what to buy or not to buy and the decision is obtained from previous activities (Assauri, 2009) . According to (Kotler, Philip & Keller, 2009) what is meant by purchasing decisions is a problem-solving process that consists of analyzing or recognizing needs and desires, searching for information, evaluating sources of selection of alternatives. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2017), consumer purchasing decisions are influenced by four main factors, namely cultural, social, personal, and psychological. To measure purchasing decisions, indicators developed by Kotler and Keller, (2009) are used, namely Attention, Interest, Desire, and Action.

Brand Awareness

Aaker (1991b) defines brand awareness as the ability of potential consumers to recognize or remember that a brand belongs to a particular product category. Brand awareness is not limited to recognizing a logo or brand name, but also includes recall of slogans, packaging colors, and even experiences interacting with the product (Krisnawati, 2016) . (Schiefer, 2008) Brand awareness is the ability of a brand to appear in consumers' minds when they think of a particular product category, as well as how easily the brand name is remembered or recognized. According to (Herdana, 2015), factors that influence brand awareness are product quality, advertising, and promotion. According to (Wilujeng, SR, & Edwar, 2014) , indicators of brand awareness are brand recall, recognition, purchase, and consumption.

Brand Image

According to (Tambrin, 2010) Brand image is a customer's perception of a brand reflected in the brand associations held in the customer's memory. (Sangadji, 2013) states that image is a concept that is easy to understand, but difficult to explain systematically because of its abstract nature. According to Rangkuti, (2004) states that brand image is a collection of associations formed in the minds of consumers. This means that brand image plays an important role in influencing how consumers view a product or company. According to Keller (2013), factors that influence the formation of brand image include: brand associations, association strength, uniqueness, and the familiarity or superiority of brand associations. According to (Aaker, 1991a) brand image consists of three indicators, namely: Product Attributes, Consumer Benefits, and Brand Personality.

Influence between variables

The Influence of Brand Awareness on Purchase Decisions

Brand awareness is a crucial factor influencing consumer purchasing decisions (Zhang et al., 2020) . Brand awareness reflects consumers' ability to recognize and recall a brand, thus serving as a basis for considering purchasing decisions (Aaker, 1991). Several studies have demonstrated a significant influence of *brand awareness* on purchasing decisions, including research by Sabilla & Yuliana, 2025. (Melinia et al., 2024) (Rachmah & Andari, 2022) and (Maulana Irfanudin et al., 2022) .

The Influence of Brand Awareness on Brand Image

Brand awareness plays a crucial role in shaping brand image because consumer awareness of a brand is the gateway to forming deeper perceptions (Rachmawati & Akbar, 2025). A high level of brand awareness will create positive consumer

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perceptions of the brand, thereby strengthening the brand image in the minds of consumers (P. Kotler & Keller, 2016). According to Keller (2013) in (Rachmawati & Akbar, 2025), brand awareness is an important foundation in building brand equity because consumers' initial awareness of a brand will influence the formation of brand image. Several studies have proven the significant influence of brand awareness on brand image, namely in research (Rachmawati, 2023) , (Henny Welsa, Ignatius Soni Kurniawan, 2022) and (Wiranata & Bernarto, 2020).

The Influence of Brand Image on Purchase Decisions

Brand image is a crucial factor influencing consumer behavior in purchasing decisions. A positive brand image will increase consumer trust, strengthen perceived quality, and ultimately drive purchasing decisions (Hanifah & Wulandari, 2021). According to P. Kotler & Keller (2016), brand image is the perception and beliefs held by consumers, reflected in the associations held in their memory towards a brand. Several studies have demonstrated a significant influence of brand awareness on brand image , including those by Lestari & Wismantoro (2024) , Sutrisno (2023) , and Natasya Aulia Putri (2023) .

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

H1: It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence of Brand Awareness on Purchasing Decisions

H2: It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence of Brand Awareness on Brand Image.

H3: It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence of Brand Image on Purchasing Decisions

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses the associative quantitative method of Causality. The sampling technique used is a non-probability sampling technique using purposive sampling. The reason for using the purposive sampling method in this study is because the variables studied require selecting samples based on certain criteria or based on special selection so that the resulting data is valid, with the criteria being 1. Consumers of Club brand bottled drinking water domiciled in Mataram City 2. Consumers aged 17 years and over because that age is assumed to be able to provide a more objective response 3. Deciding for themselves to buy Club brand bottled drinking water. The population in this study are consumers who have purchased Club brand bottled drinking water in Mataram City with a sample size of 100 respondents because the researcher made the determination of the minimum number of samples calculated using the Ferdinand formula (2014: 173) which says the number of samples is the number of indicators multiplied by 5 to 10. In this study using 11 indicators, the number obtained is 100 - 200. This study will use 100 samples because it can be considered representative. The data collection method in this research is a sample survey. The data collection technique uses questionnaires and surveys. Offline. Questions were structured based on indicators for each research variable using a Likert scale of 1-5. The data obtained were then analyzed using statistical analysis methods with SmartPLS software version 4.1.1.5.

IV. DISCUSSION

Respondent Characteristics

Based on the results of a survey of 100 respondents using a distributed questionnaire, a description of the respondents' characteristics, including gender, age, and occupation, was obtained. The following is a description of each respondent's characteristics:

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Table 4.1 Respondent Characteristics

No	Characteristics		Number of people)	%
	Gender	Woman	68	68%
		Man	32	32%
	Amount		100	100%
	Age	17-22 years	64	64%
		23-28 years old	34	32%
		29-34 years	0	0
		>35 years	2	2%
	Amount		100	100%
	Work	Students	63	63%
		Entrepreneur/Businessman	17	17%
		Civil Servants/Private	10	10%
		Employees	10	10%
		Other		
	Amount		100	100%
	Frequency of purchasing Club brand AMDK	1-2 times	16	16%
		2-5 times	65	65%
		>5 times	19	19%
	Amount		100	100%

Source: Processed Primary Data

Based on Table 4.1, it can be concluded that the heterogeneity of the respondents is assumed to be representative of the Club consumer population.

Research Analysis and Results

The research data was processed using SmartPLS software version 4.1.1.5. Model testing in PLS-SEM aims to predict and develop theories. Furthermore, PLS is also used to confirm theories on relationships between variables that already have a strong theoretical basis (theoretical testing). The processed data will be analyzed in two ways: evaluation of the measurement model (outer model) and evaluation of the structural model (inner model). The results of the outer model and inner model measurements in PLS-SEM are as follows:

Figure 4.1 Structural Model

a. Evaluation of the Measurement Model (Outer Model)

To evaluate the measurement model, two tests will be carried out, namely the validity test and the reliability test.

1. Validity Test

In SmartPLS, validity testing can be seen from the convergent and discriminant validity values. Convergent validity consists of two components: outer loading and AVE, while discriminant validity also consists of two components: Fornell-Larcker and cross-loading. The following are the results of the validity test analysis:

a. Convergent Validity

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Convergent validity is used to determine the correlation between item scores or component scores and construct scores. An individual's reflective measure is considered high if the correlation (outer loading) is >0.7 with the construct being measured. Convergent validity can also be assessed from the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value, with a rule of thumb of $AVE >0.5$. The results of the convergent validity test are shown in the following table:

Table 4.2 Loading factor values for each indicator on its respective variable

NO	Variables	Item	Loading Factor	Keterangan
	Brand Awareness (X)	X1	0,845	Valid
		X2	0,894	Valid
		X3	0,863	Valid
		X4	0,718	Valid
		X5	0,819	Valid
		X6	0,816	Valid
		X7	0,905	Valid
		X8	0,887	Valid
	Purchase Decisions (Y)	Y1	0,921	Valid
		Y2	0,910	Valid
		Y3	0,859	Valid
		Y4	0,906	Valid
		Y5	0,942	Valid
		Y6	0,921	Valid
		Y7	0,892	Valid
		Y8	0,865	Valid
	Brand Image (Z)	Z1	0,887	Valid
		Z2	0,905	Valid
		Z3	0,917	Valid
		Z4	0,939	Valid
		Z5	0,942	Valid
		Z6	0,892	Valid

Source: Primary Data processed 2025

The outer factor is a coefficient that describes the level of relationship between an indicator and its latent variable. In general, the higher the outer factor value, the better the relationship, or the more valid it is. A good outer factor value is considered valid if its value is above 0.70. Based on Table 4.2, the outer factor values for all indicators relative to their latent variables are above 0.70. This indicates that all indicators in this study have a valid relationship with their latent variables.

Table 4.3 Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variables	AVE value	AVE Value Limit	Decision
Brand Awareness (X)	0.715	0.500	Fulfilled
Purchase Decision (Y)	0.814	0.500	Fulfilled
Brand Image (Z)	0.832	0.500	Fulfilled

Source: Primary Data processed 2025

Table 4.3 above shows that the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value for Brand Awareness, Purchasing Decisions, and Brand Image has produced an AVE value greater than 0.500. Therefore, it can be concluded that the indicators used in the study are valid because they have met the requirements for convergent validity.

2. Discriminant Validity Test

In this study, the discriminant validity of the measurement model with indicator reflection can be assessed based on cross-loading measurements with the construct. If the cross-loading value for each indicator is greater than the cross-loading value for other

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latent variables (> 0.5), it can be said to be valid (Supriyanto & Maharani, 2013). The cross-loading values in this study are presented in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4 Cross Loading Value Results

	Brand Awareness (X)	Purchase Decision (Y)	Brand Image (Z)
X.1	0.845	0.723	0.567
X.2	0.894	0.738	0.637
X.3	0.863	0.694	0.628
X.4	0.718	0.605	0.637
X.5	0.819	0.601	0.555
X.6	0.816	0.611	0.568
X.7	0.905	0.758	0.636
X.8	0.887	0.773	0.650
And .1	0.840	0.921	0.790
Y.2	0.757	0.910	0.783
Y.3	0.733	0.859	0.686
Y.4	0.727	0.906	0.764
Y.5	0.724	0.942	0.801
Y.6	0.752	0.921	0.734
Y.7	0.713	0.892	0.739
Y.8	0.644	0.865	0.687
Z.1	0.700	0.726	0.877
Z.2	0.696	0.714	0.905
Z.3	0.675	0.769	0.917
Z.4	0.675	0.807	0.939
Z.5	0.628	0.788	0.942
Z.6	0.575	0.740	0.892

Source: Primary Data processed 2025

Based on Table 4.4 above, it can be concluded that the indicator loading value of a variable is greater than the cross-loading value. Therefore, the validity test results above meet the requirements for discriminant validity testing, thus declaring this study valid.

3. Composite Reliability Test

The calculation of the composite reliability value is done by looking at the composite reliability value of the indicators that measure the variable value, and the indicator will have a good composite reliability value if the value is > 0.7 or it can be concluded that the variable has fulfilled the aspects and the indicators are consistent or reliable in presenting the latent variable.

Table 4.5 Composite Reliability Test Results

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Decision
X	0.942	0.945	0.952	Reliable
Y	0.967	0.969	0.972	Reliable
Z	0.960	0.960	0.967	Reliable

Source: Primary Data processed 2025

Based on the results of the Composite Reliability test of the instrument in table 4.5 above, it shows that all constructs for all questions in the 100 questionnaires on the statement items in the variables of Brand Awareness, Purchase Decision and Brand Image have composite reliability values > 0.70 and Cronbach alpha > 0.60 . Therefore, it can be concluded that all constructs have high or good reliability values.

Structural Model (Inner Model)

R-Square (R^2)

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In this study, the R-square values used were 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 to conclude that strong, moderate, and weak models existed (Ghozali 2015). However, the higher the R-square value, the greater the significance of the variable.

Table 4.6 R-Square Value Results

	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Purchase Decision (Y)	0.790	0.785
Brand Image (Z)	0.522	0.517

Source: Primary Data processed 2025

Based on Table 4.6, the R Square value is 0.790, which means that 79% of consumer purchasing decisions can be explained by brand awareness, while the remaining 21% is influenced by other factors outside the research model, such as price, promotion, and lifestyle. Therefore, the R Square value for the purchasing decision variable can be categorized as strong. The R Square value obtained for the brand image variable is 0.522, indicating that 52.2% of the variation in brand image can be explained by brand awareness, while the remaining 47.8% is influenced by other factors outside the research model, such as price, promotion, and lifestyle. Thus, the R Square value for the brand image variable can be categorized as moderate.

Q-Square

Goodness of fit is assessed from the Q-square value. It is said that the higher the Q-square value, the better the model fits the data. The results of the Q-square calculation in this study are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Q-Square} &= 1 - [(1 - R^2_1) \times (1 - R^2_2)] \\
 &= 1 - [(1 - 0.790) \times (1 - 0.522)] \\
 &= 1 - (0.21 \times 0.48) \\
 &= \mathbf{0.89}
 \end{aligned}$$

The calculation results obtained a Q-square value of 0.89. This value indicates that the research model has high predictive relevance, meaning that 89% of the data variation can be predicted well by the model. This confirms that the structural model has good goodness of fit and is suitable for use in predicting the relationship between brand awareness, brand image, and purchasing decisions.

Hypothesis Testing

The basis used in testing the hypothesis is the value generated from the bootstrapping process. Table 4.7 provides the estimated output for hypothesis testing with path analysis. The path coefficient is used to measure the direct influence of an independent variable on the dependent variable in a model with a value range of -1 to 1. This value works by indicating the direction of the relationship on the variable, whether the influence is positive or negative. Meanwhile, the P-value is used to measure the level of significance of the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Where this relationship will be significant if the P-value is smaller than the alpha value ($P\text{-value} \leq \alpha$). In this study, the alpha value (α) is 0.050 or 5%. Based on Table 4.13, the path coefficient value for each variable will be interpreted as follows:

Tabel 4.7 Nilai Path Coefficient

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	DESCRIPTION
X -> Y	0.456	0.462	0.077	5.946	0.000	Significant
X -> Z	0.722	0.717	0.065	11.100	0.000	Significant
Z -> Y	0.501	0.494	0.078	6.387	0.000	Significant

Source: Primary Data processed 2025

Based on Table 4.7 it can be seen that:

1. The Brand Awareness variable P-value is 0, where the value is <0.05 , meaning the hypothesis **is accepted**, thus this study accepts the first hypothesis (H1). This indicates that brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions.
2. The Brand Awareness variable has a P-value of 0, where the value is <0.05 , meaning the hypothesis **is accepted**, thus this study accepts the second hypothesis (H2). This indicates that brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on brand image.

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3. The Brand Image variable P-value is 0, where the value is <0.05 , meaning the hypothesis is **accepted**, thus this study accepts the third hypothesis (H3). This indicates that brand image has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. Based on the results of the path analysis shown in Table 4.7 it is known that the Brand Awareness variable has a significant influence on Purchasing Decisions, both directly and indirectly through Brand Image as a mediating variable. The direct influence of Brand Awareness on Purchasing Decisions is indicated by a coefficient value of 0.456, with a T-statistic value of 5.946 and a p-value of 0.000, which means it is significant at the 95% awareness level. This indicates that the higher the Brand Awareness, the higher the Purchasing Decision directly, without having to go through other intermediary factors. On the other hand, the indirect influence of Brand Awareness on Purchasing Decisions through Brand Image is also significant, with a coefficient value of 0.362, a T-statistic of 5.551, and a p-value of 0.000. This means that Brand Awareness can also increase Purchasing Decisions indirectly, by first building a brand image. Based on the results of the analysis, the Brand Awareness variable has a direct and indirect influence on Purchasing Decisions. The direct effect of Brand Awareness on Purchasing Decisions has a coefficient of 0.456 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating a positive and significant relationship. Meanwhile, the indirect effect of Brand Awareness on Purchasing Decisions through Brand Image is also significant, with a coefficient of 0.362 and a p-value of 0.000. Since both direct (X→Y) and indirect (X→Z→Y) paths are equally significant, it can be concluded that Brand Image partially mediates the relationship between Brand Awareness and Purchasing Decisions. This means that increasing Brand Awareness can encourage Purchasing Decisions both directly and through the formation of a positive brand image first. In other words, the higher consumer awareness of the Club brand, the stronger the brand image formed, and this will strengthen the consumer's decision to purchase the product.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the data analysis carried out using the variables studied, the calculation results were obtained which can be explained as follows:

The Influence of Brand Awareness on Purchase Decision

The relationship between brand awareness and purchasing decisions can be explained through consumer behavior theory, where brand awareness is the initial stage in the consumer decision process. According to (Kotler & Keller, 2016), before consumers decide to purchase, they go through the stages of recognizing needs, seeking information, and evaluating alternatives. Brands with a high level of awareness will appear more frequently in consumers' consideration sets, which are the collection of brands that are actually considered for purchase. Therefore, the higher the consumer awareness of the Club brand, the greater the chance that the brand will be chosen over its competitors.

This means that the higher the level of consumer awareness of the Club brand, the more likely consumers are to purchase Club-branded bottled water products. Brand awareness reflects consumers' ability to recognize and recall a brand (brand recall). In this study, many respondents stated that when thinking of bottled drinking water, the Club brand immediately came to mind. This indicates that Club has succeeded in creating a strong brand association in consumers' minds, both through its logo, packaging color, and widespread product distribution. Furthermore, recognition also plays a significant role. Consumers can easily recognize Club products on store shelves without seeing the brand name, simply from the packaging and color. This ability to recognize provides a sense of familiarity and comfort, which ultimately strengthens and encourages purchase intention (interest and desire). In terms of purchase and consumption indicators, the study results show that consumers often repurchase Club products because they are used to consuming them. This repeated consumption habit indicates that high awareness has developed into a stable purchasing preference. Meanwhile, in the Purchasing Decision variable which is measured through the attention, interest, desire, and action indicators, respondents stated that they noticed the club brand on the store shelf (attention), were interested in knowing more about the product (interest), had the desire to buy because it was considered safe and fresh (desire), and finally decided to buy (action).

Thus, the positive relationship between Brand Awareness and Purchasing Decisions can be explained by the easier it is for consumers to remember and recognize a club brand (brand recall & recognition), the higher their attention, interest, and purchasing actions (attention and action) towards the product. These results reinforce the view (Kotler & Keller, 2016) which states that high brand awareness creates a sense of trust and reduces purchasing risk. In other words, the higher the Brand Awareness, the stronger the consumer's urge to make a purchase.

This result is supported by research (Sabilla & Yuliana, 2025) which states that brand awareness has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions for Wardah brand products, this is in line with research (Melinia et al., 2024) which states that brand awareness has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions for Kopi Kenangan, Palembang branch.

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The Influence of Brand Awareness on Brand Image

Brand awareness serves as the initial bridge in building a brand image. According to Aaker (1991a), a high level of awareness allows a brand to enter consumers' long-term memory, which then becomes the basis for building positive associations and perceptions of product quality. In other words, when consumers consistently know and recognize a club brand, they will also perceive the brand as having good values, benefits, and personality. This means that the higher the level of brand awareness a consumer has, the more positive the brand image formed in the consumer's mind. Strong brand awareness makes consumers more familiar with the product, understand its characteristics, and assess its quality positively. When consumers are able to remember and recognize the Club brand easily (brand recall and recognition), they begin to form perceptions of product attributes such as water quality, packaging design, and market availability. For example, respondents considered Club drinking water easy to find in various sales outlets and at an affordable price, which created the image of Club as a practical, economical, and accessible brand. Furthermore, the consumer benefits indicator was also reflected in respondents' responses, who stated that consuming Club drinking water made them feel healthy and fresh, and fulfilled the need for hygienic products. The higher the consumer awareness of the Club brand, the stronger their belief in the benefits provided by the product. The brand personality indicator is seen from consumers' views that Club is a brand that consistently maintains the quality and freshness of its products. This means that brand awareness not only makes consumers familiar with the product but also forms a positive impression of the brand personality. Thus, the positive relationship between Brand Awareness and Brand Image can be explained by the fact that the more frequently consumers remember and recognize the Club brand, the stronger their positive perceptions of product attributes, benefits, and brand personality. This finding aligns with the theory (Aaker, 1991b) that states that brand awareness is the main foundation in building a strong brand image. This result is supported by research (Rachmawati & Akbar, 2025) which states that brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on brand image, and (Wiranata & Bernarto, 2020) stated that brand awareness plays an important role in building brand image because the more frequently consumers interact with the brand, the stronger the positive perception that is formed.

The Influence of Brand Image on Purchase Decision

Brand image is a consumer's perception of a brand formed from the experiences, beliefs, and impressions the product leaves in their minds. Brand image is an important psychological factor that influences consumer behavior in making purchasing decisions. The more positive a brand's image is, the higher the consumer's tendency to choose and purchase that product compared to its competitors. The relationship between brand image and purchasing decisions can be explained through consumer behavior theory, where brand image acts as a form of perceived value. According to (Kotler & Keller, 2016), consumer purchasing decisions are not only driven by the functional factors of the product, but also by the perception and image attached to the brand. When consumers perceive a brand as having a good reputation and matching their personality, they will be more confident in choosing that product over other brands. This study shows that a positive brand image will boost consumer trust and increase interest in purchasing products. Consumers perceive the Club brand as having a good image because it is easy to find, affordable, and perceived as a safe and hygienic product. Product attributes indicators show that consumers perceive Club branded products as easy to find, good quality, and affordable. Positive perceptions of these product attributes generate attention and interest because consumers are drawn to and pay attention to the product while shopping. Consumer benefits indicators show that consumers perceive Club products as providing direct benefits, such as a fresh taste and guaranteed cleanliness. When the benefits are felt to be real, a desire or desire to repurchase arises due to satisfaction. Brand personality reflects how consumers perceive Club as a consistent, trustworthy brand with a good reputation in the community. This strong brand personality image fosters consumer trust and influences action, namely the actual decision to purchase. Thus, the more positive the brand image formed through attributes, benefits, and brand personality, the higher the consumer's purchasing decision.

These results are supported by research (Hanifah & Wulandari, 2021) which states that a strong brand image can increase confidence and purchasing decisions for a product. These results indicate that brand image plays a crucial role as a link between perception and action, where a positive image encourages consumers to trust, be interested in, and ultimately make purchases of the Club brand. In line with research (Lestari & Wismanoro, 2024) which states that brand image has a positive and significant influence on Wardah lipstick purchasing decisions, (Sutrisno, 2023) states that brand image has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions for street boba drinks.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on research results and data analysis regarding the influence of brand awareness on brand image and purchasing decisions, the following conclusions can be drawn:

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1. Brand awareness has a positive and significant influence on brand image for Club Brand Bottled Drinking Water in Mataram City. This means that the higher the level of brand awareness, the higher the purchasing decision for Club Brand Bottled Drinking Water.
2. Brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on the brand image of Club Brand Bottled Drinking Water in Mataram City. This means that the higher the level of brand awareness, the higher the brand image of Club Brand Bottled Drinking Water.
3. Brand image has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions for Club brand bottled water in Mataram City. This means that the higher the brand image, the higher the purchasing decision for Club brand bottled water.

Research Suggestions

Based on the research results, discussions and conclusions obtained, the suggestions that can be given are as follows:

1. For further research, there are several things that are suggested, including:
 - a. This study found that the influence of the independent variable, Brand Awareness, on purchasing decisions still left behind the influence of other variables such as price, promotion, and lifestyle, amounting to 21% outside the research model. Therefore, it is recommended that future researchers add or combine other variables, such as price, promotion, and lifestyle, that could potentially influence purchasing decisions.
 - b. The use of questionnaires in this study only provides closed statements so that there are likely things that cannot be obtained from respondents, it would be better if the following study added open statements.
 - c. Directed at other research objects, in order to compare how the level of brand awareness and brand image influence purchasing decisions on different products.
2. For companies, there are several things that need to be considered, namely the following:
 - a. Club is expected to maintain and enhance the brand values and identity it has built since its inception. These values are the hallmarks that distinguish Club from other bottled water brands. Consistently maintaining product quality and a positive brand image will help strengthen Club's position in the market and increase consumer awareness.
 - b. Based on the research results, the product attributes indicator in the brand image variable has the highest influence on consumer perception. This indicates that product quality, packaging labeling, and brand recognition are the main factors in shaping a positive image of the Club brand. Therefore, the company needs to continuously ensure product quality and maintain water quality standards, as well as innovate its packaging to ensure it remains attractive and easily recognized by consumers.
 - c. Meanwhile, the consumption indicator for the brand awareness variable showed the lowest average value. This indicates that some consumers have not yet developed a habit of consistently repurchasing Club products. Therefore, the company needs to strengthen its promotional strategies and consumer loyalty programs, such as repeat purchase discounts, collaborations with retail stores, or campaigns that encourage sustainable consumption habits. These efforts are expected to increase repeat purchase frequency and strengthen the Club brand's position in the bottled water market.

REFERENCES

- 1) Aaker, D. A. (1991a). *Managing brand equity : Capitalizing on the value of a brand name*. Anastasia Anggi Fernanda, Usep Suhud, & Daru Putri Kusumaningtyas. (2025). *Studi Tentang Brand Awareness pada Bodycare Halal di Social Commerce dan Dampaknya terhadap*.
- 2) Aaker, D. A. (1991b). *Managing brand equity : Capitalizing on the value of a brand name*.
- 3) Assauri, S. (2009). *Manajemen Pemasaran Dasar, Konsep dan Strategi, Edisi Pertama Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Aziz*.
- 4) Emma K. Macdonald. (2000). Brand Awareness Effects on Consumer Decision Making for a Common, Repeat Purchase Product: A Replication. *Endocrinology*, 93(4), 925–931. <https://doi.org/10.1210/endo-93-4-925>
- 5) Hanifah, N., & Wulandari, R. (2021). The Influence Of Online Customer Review On Purchase Decision With Trust as Variabel Intervening In Shopee. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Management Research*, 5(7), 166–182.
- 6) Henny Welsa, Ignatius Soni Kurniawan, F. I. M. (2022). *PENGARUH BRAND AWARENESS TERHADAP CUSTOMER LOYALTY DENGAN BRAND IMAGE DAN RELATIONSHIP QUALITY SEBAGAI VARIABEL INTERVENING (studi kasus konsumen penjualan sangkar burung Ebod Jaya)*.
- 7) Herdana, A. (2015). *Analisis Pengaruh Kesadaran Merek (Brand Awareness) Pada Produk Asuransi Jiwa Prudential Life Assurance (Studi Pada Pru Passion Agency Jakarta)*. *Jurnal Riset Bisnis dan Manajemen*, 3(1), 1-18.
- 8) Keller, K. L. (2013). *Strategic Brand Management: Building, Measuring, and Managing Brand Equity. 4th Edition*. Pearson Education.

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- 9) Kotler, Philip & Keller, L. K. (2009). *Manajemen pemasaran, edisi 13*. Jakarta: Erlangga, 14.
- 10) Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). *Marketing Management Global Edition* (Vol. 15E). <https://doi.org/10.1080/08911760903022556>
- 11) Krisnawati, D. (2016). Pengaruh Brand Awareness Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Amdk Merek Aqua (Studi Pada Masyarakat Di Kota Bandung). *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis Krisnadwipayana*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.35137/jmbk.v4i1.30>
- 12) Lestari, M., & Wismanoro, Y. (2024). Pengaruh Brand Image, Harga, Brand Trust Dan Kualitas Produk Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Lipstik Wardah Di Kota Semarang. *Jurnal Maneksi*, 13(1), 233–241. <https://doi.org/10.31959/jm.v13i1.2188>
- 13) Maulana Irfanudin, A., Andalusi, R., & Jamil, I. (2022). Pengaruh Brand Awareness dan Promosi Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Produk. *Jurnal Disrupsi Bisnis*, 5(3), 237–247. <http://openjournal.unpam.ac.id/index.php/DRB/index>
<http://openjournal.unpam.ac.id/index.php/DRB/index>
- 14) Melinia, F., Mavilinda, H. F., & Rosa, A. (2024). Pengaruh Brand Awareness Dan Perceived Quality Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Pada Kopi Kenangan Cabang Kota Palembang. *Jurnal Media Wahana Ekonomika*, 21(2), 246–255. <https://doi.org/10.31851/jmwe.v21i2.16118>
- 15) Moisescu, O. I. (2009). *The Importance of Brand Awareness in Consumers' Buying Decision and Perceived Risk Assessment*. *Management & Marketing*, 7(1), 103–110.
- 16) Natasya Aulia Putri. (2023). Pengaruh Kualitas Produk, Harga, Dan Citra Merek Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Lipstik Wardah. *Maeswara : Jurnal Riset Ilmu Manajemen Dan Kewirausahaan*, 1(5), 151–160. <https://doi.org/10.61132/maeswara.v1i5.187>
- 17) Pratiwi, J., Asiati I, D., & Fitantina. (2025). *Kata Kunci : Produk, Promosi dan Keputusan Pembelian*. 2(6), 555–564.
- 18) Putri, D. A., Nurhayati., & Firdaus. (2024). *The Influence of Social Media Marketing and Brand Awareness on Purchasing Decisions with Brand Image as a Mediating Variable in Kopi Kenangan*.
- 19) Rachmah, F., & Andari, T. (2022). Pengaruh Brand Awerenes Perceived Quality dan Brand Loyalty Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Ban Hankood PT Budiyaniti Semesta Group di Cikarang. *Karimah Tauhid*, 1(6), 767–776.
- 20) Rachmawati. (2023). *Service Quality, Brand Awareness, Consumer Experience, and Sustainability in Shaping Promotion and Brand Image*.
- 21) Rachmawati, E., & Akbar, H. (2025). Brand Awareness and Sustainability in Shaping Promotion Strategies in Indonesia. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis*, 16(1), 89–110. <https://doi.org/10.18196/mb.v16i1.24545>
- 22) Rania, C., Daud, I., Afifah, N., Heriyadi, H., & Syahbandi, S. (2023). The Role of Brand Awareness as a Mediating Variable on the Effect of Instagram Advertisement and Word of Mouth on Purchase Decision (Case Study in Erigo). *South Asian Research Journal of Business and Management*, 5(1), 27–34. <https://doi.org/10.36346/sarjbm.2023.v05i01.004>
- 23) Rosmayanti, M. (2023). Pengaruh Brand Image Dan Brand Awareness Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Konsumen Mixue. *Journal on Education*, 5(3), 8126–8137. <https://doi.org/10.31004/joe.v5i3.1600>
- 24) Sabilla, E. F. N., & Yuliana, L. (2025). Pengaruh Brand Awareness dan Brand Reputation terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Produk Merek Wardah. *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis Madani*, 7(1), 29–43. <https://doi.org/10.51353/jmbm.v7i1.1002>
- 25) Sangadji, E. M. (2013). *Perilaku Konsumen; Pendekatan praktis disertai himpunan jurnal penelitian*.
- 26) Schiefer, J. (2008). *Global and local brand positioning: a company and consumer perspective*. na.
- 27) Sutrisno. (2023). Analisis Pengaruh Brand Image Dan Brand Awareness Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Produk Minuman Street Boba. *Management Studies and Entrepreneurship Journal*, 4(1), 571–578. <http://journal.yrpiiku.com/index.php/msej>
- 28) Tambrin, M. (2010). *Pengaruh Brand Image Terhadap Pelanggan Kartu Simpati Terhadap Kepuasan Mahasiswa Universitas Trunojoyo Madura*. *Jurnal Studi Manajemen*, 4(1), 4–8.
- 29) Widiawara, T. (2017). ANALISIS PENGARUH KUALITAS PRODUK DAN CITRA MEREK TERHADAP LOYALITAS PELANGGAN MELALUI KEPUASAN PELANGGAN SEBAGAI VARIABEL INTERVENING (Studi pada Pelanggan Air Minum Dalam Kemasan Club di Semarang). *Diponegoro Journal of Management*, 6, 1–15. <http://ejournal-s1.undip.ac.id/index.php/dbr>
- 30) Wilujeng, S. R., & Edwar, M. (2014). *Pengaruh Brand Awareness dan Brand Trust Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Produk Oriflame*. *Jurnal Pendidikan Tata Niaga*, 2(2), 1-15.
- 31) Wiranata & Bernarto. (2020). *"The Influence of Brand Awareness, Perceived Quality, and Brand Image on Brand Loyalty: Brand Image as a Mediating Variable."*
- 32) Zhang, Y., Fang, Y., Wei, K., & Wang, H. (2020). *The Influences of Brand Awareness on Consumers' Cognitive Process: An Event-related Potentials Study*. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 14, 571.